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In this Earth of many layers have I realized in my few short years that there are billions of trillions of energies and properties of vibrations, frequencies, of different planes and dimensions. Quickly realized among viewing other animals and seemingly in some similar ways, humans who behaved more like animals responded in a adversarial response. I knew that in the higher functions of my mind something needed to be taken in closer observation on a molecular sub atomic, atomic, level to macro level and moving to environmental. The level of regression or transformation into different energies and connecting into mindsets there had to be a reason.

Deoxyribonucleic acid/ DNA is in our bodies and there is a blueprint for who we are and instructions on who we will become. Example dealing with eye color and growing in various ways almost down to the T.

Many people believe who we are and no matter what there is no changing as the sole determinant, in other words *genetic determinism* there is some explaining to do that is flawed in other words.

In the scope of epigenetics goes into the science on the inter workings of development

functioning evolution influenced by various forces that do operate or in operation outside of the DNA sequence, including intracellular, environmental and energetic influence. There are many ways to implement change to the human mind and body to be as a catalyst to speed up and change that person or group and even nations of the earth involving a better greater unified human race.

In the 1950's researchers and scientists have embraced to accept that epigenetic influence is vital in our development. Epi – Greek for “besides” – combines with the word, genetics, to essentially mean “something more than genetics.” That “something more” is widely held today to ask our surroundings – thus meaning that our ordering and therefore the environment during which we develop determine who and what we are.

We can change our DNA landscape , there is a difference of genetic determinism and epigenetics, and is critical to know and understand the difference. *“The difference between these two is significant because this fundamental belief called genetic determinism literally*

means that our lives, which are defined as our physical, physiological and emotional behavioral traits, are controlled by the genetic code,” Bruce Lipton

Thinking that genes have superior control only leave room to operate in a victim mindset of passed genes handed down. Those attributes and outcomes potentially we can change altogether. Our body is a system and positive feelings or emotions fortify or reinforce our energy system and nourish the body at a

cellular level this can catalytic results or inhibiting results. In other words speed up or slow down transformation. Evidence and proven experimental evidence to support the hypothesis that DNA molecule can be altered through intention. It's a modulation of DNA.

The heart, which generates a much stronger electromagnetic field than the brain's, provides the energetic field that binds together the higher dimensional structures and the body's many systems as well as its DNA. Childre's theory of heart intelligence proposes that "individuals who are able to maintain states of heart coherence have increased coupling to the higher dimensional structures and would thus be more able to produce changes in the DNA. The influence or control individuals can have on their DNA – who and what they are and will become – is further illuminated in Doc Childre's theory of heart intelligence. Childre postulates that "an energetic connection or coupling of information" occurs between the DNA in cells and higher dimensional structures – the higher self or spirit."

Gene modulation

Gene regulation is an important part of normal development. Genes are turned on and off in different patterns during development to make a brain cell look and act different from a liver cell or a muscle cell, for example. Gene regulation also allows cells to react quickly to changes in their environments.

Each cell expresses, or activates, only a fraction of its genes. the remainder of the genes are repressed, or turned off. the method of turning genes on and off is understood as gene regulation. Gene regulation is a crucial a part of normal development. Genes are turned

on and off in several patterns during development to form a nerve cell look and act different from a liver cell or a muscle fiber , for instance . Gene regulation also allows cells to react quickly

to changes in their environments. Although we all know that the regulation of genes is critical for all times, this complex process isn't yet fully understood.

Gene regulation can occur at any point during organic phenomenon, but most ordinarily occurs at the extent of transcription (when the knowledge during a gene's DNA is transferred to mRNA). Signals from the environment or from other cells activate proteins called transcription factors. These proteins bind to regulatory regions of a gene and increase or decrease the extent of transcription. By controlling the extent of transcription, this process can determine the quantity of protein product that's made by a gene at any given time.

Predictive Medicine

Some experts give way to new beliefs after knowledge of human genetics to revolutionize medical practice.

Here are a few of those belief findings:

- Genetic profile information of the people that will most likely rate possibility to have a response to drugs, or an important factor is being potentially harmed by drugs pharmacogenetics
- New pathways of understanding will lead to classification of diseases of biochemistry and not just symptoms.
- Early option to susceptibility of prevention, multifactorial diseases, coronary heart disease hypertension, stroke, cancer, diabetes and others.

The Guthrie test, known as the PKU test, is a diagnostic tool to test infants for Phenylketonuria a few days after birth. To administer the Guthrie test, doctors

use Guthrie cards to collect capillary blood from an infant's heel, and the cards are saved for later testing. On the whole, though, it works. Although PKU is fairly rare (around 1 in 15 000 live births), it used to account for roughly one per cent of profound mental retardation. Screening has practically eliminated this.

Cystic Fibrosis

A different model for the genetic tests of the longer term is screening for CF (CF). this is often a DNA-based test, which became possible after the gene involved in CF was identified in 1989. CF may be a recessive disease, and it should be easy to check to ascertain if prospective parents carry a mutated allele. an easy mouthwash yields enough cells for DNA extraction. If both partners are carriers, they will consider further counselling before conception, and/or pre-natal testing of any potentially affected fetus.

Even simple disorders are arising to be not so simple. There are now known to be quite 900 different mutations within the gene for CF. Many are rare, but even the simplest (and most expensive) testing currently envisaged would identify only about 85% of couples in danger . In terms of susceptibility (The term 'genetic risk factor' refers to a susceptible disease allele and should not be confused with 'risk

factor', meaning an 'environmental factor'. Both genetic risk factors and risk factors increase the risk of an individual developing a particular disease.)